

INTERDISCIPLINARY CONTEXTUALIZATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL IN GRADE 7 MATHEMATICS

Karen Mae L. Elen

Mathematics Department, Mandurriao National High School, Iloilo City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11639665>

ABSTRACT

This developmental research aimed to create interdisciplinary contextualized instructional material in mathematics for Grade 7 students. The progress was based on the Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate (ADDIE) Model. The analyze, design, and develop stages were done with the data gathered from observations and interviews of two Grade 7 mathematics teachers, and two department heads from two public schools in Iloilo. The participants suggested to develop an activity book for fourth quarter topics that focused on statistics concepts. For the implementation stage, an activity book was pilot tested in one Grade 7 section composed of 50 students. The evaluation stage involved expert's rating of the material's acceptability and the students' satisfaction. Mean and standard deviation were used in the analysis. The results showed that the developed material was highly acceptable, and the students' satisfaction was also highly satisfied. The activity book was clearly an appropriate material for interdisciplinary contextualization in the classroom. Experimental studies may be done in order to ascertain the effectiveness of the developed material.

Keywords: *Interdisciplinary Contextualization, ADDIE Model, Activity Book, Acceptability, Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

The belief was inculcated in everyone's mind that Mathematics becomes harder as time goes by (Thompson, 1994) which turn into notion that affects and limits the

students' mathematical performance. It creates a mental barrier that significantly impacts individual's performance and attitude towards the subject. Heckman & Weissglass (1994) believed that Mathematics will be learned by more students if: (1) taught with other subjects in a real-world context, (2) practical learning apprenticeships are developed, and (3) educators articulate and challenge their own beliefs and values about Mathematics, learning, and teaching. This suggests that teachers should use available resources in their locality and within the context of the students so that they could relate and appreciate the real context of Mathematics. This supports the study of Barrido (2015) that the student learns best when he acts on objects and events within his environment and in the process, gains understanding and derives meaning of those objects and events. Also, Akande (1985) claims that learning can occur through one's interaction with one's environment which refers to facilities that are available to facilitate students learning outcome.

The DOST-SEI and MATHTED, Inc. (2011a) expounded that the goal of Mathematics education in the Philippines is mathematical empowerment. The goal encompasses skills and one of those skills is making mathematical connections. They also promote Interdisciplinary Contextualization (ICon) which defined as connecting/linking concepts/skills within learning areas (e.g., Math or Science) and across learning areas (e.g. Math and Science and Others). In fact, many universities are making campus wide efforts to teach interdisciplinary courses that often adopt contextual learning as a way to integrate course content (Curry, et. al., 2012). Interdisciplinary contextualization is connecting and reinforcing the subject matter rather separate and unrelated (Chernus & Fowler cited by Tan, 2016). This allows instructors and students to make broad and easy connections among disciplines, even those with distant epistemologies (Nikitina, 2002) and it achieves broad external connections between distant disciplinary shores (Nikitina and Mansilla, 2003). Nikitina (2002) identified that uncovering the difference in the underlying assumptions of different disciplines helps the instructor and the student see different systems of knowledge as complementary or connected as ways of making meaning of the world around us. Interdisciplinary contextualization strengthens learning by providing students with a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and preparing them for success in a rapidly changing world.

Aramide and Bolarinwe, cited by Adipo (2015), opine those instructional materials have the potential for enhancing students learning. The use of instructional materials in teaching and learning of Mathematics makes students to learn more and retain better what they have been taught and it also promotes and sustains students' interest (Adebanjo as cited in Adebule and Ayoola, 2015). These serve as support system of the teacher in imparting the lesson and aid in cultivating the teaching and learning process in mathematics.

Without seeing the practical applications of math, students might find it abstract and irrelevant, which can diminish their interest and engagement. This gap in teaching and learning mathematics pushes the researcher to conduct this research study. The researcher aims to develop an instructional material that provide a richer, more engaging learning experience for students. In the context of grade 7 mathematics, interdisciplinary

contextualization can help students see the relevance of math in different areas of their lives and academic pursuits.

Research Questions

This study aims to develop instructional material in Mathematics that integrate interdisciplinary contextualization. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following:

1. What are the features of an interdisciplinary contextualized instructional material in Mathematics?
2. What is the level of acceptability of interdisciplinary contextualized instructional material in terms of:
 - a. physical aspects
 - b. objectives
 - c. learning activities
 - d. evaluation procedure; and
 - e. integration of interdisciplinary contextualization.
3. What is the students' level of satisfaction of the Math 7 interdisciplinary contextualized instructional material in general in terms of:
 - a. physical aspects
 - b. pedagogical uses
 - c. evaluation procedure; and
 - d. relevance to the real-world context.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a Type 1 developmental research. This category typically involves situations in which the product development process used in a particular situation is described and analyzed and the final product is evaluated (Richey, Klein, and Nelson, 2015). The progress was based on the Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate (ADDIE) Model.

This research was composed of two intact classes of Grade 7 students from two schools in Iloilo of School Year 2017-2018. The two schools were chosen purposively through the qualification of having a large number of the student population. Two grade 7 Mathematics teachers and two head Mathematics teachers from these schools were also included as participants of this study. Moreover, in evaluation phase, six experts were included in which two experts for each field of expertise (Grade 7 Mathematics, production of instructional materials, and interdisciplinary contextualization) and 1 intact class to each school.

The data gathered from the thorough interviews with the teachers and objective classroom observations were the bases in developing the instructional material.

Thematic analysis was used for the qualitative data. Means and standard deviations were used to analyze quantitative data.

Figure 1. The research procedure

RESULTS

Table 1 summarizes the features in developing instructional material implemented in interdisciplinary contextualized mathematics.

Table 1

Features in Developing Instructional Material Implemented in Interdisciplinary Contextualized Mathematics

Features		Descriptions	Sources of Data	Sample Extracts	Coded
Students' Environment/Status	Common	Slum areas and poverty status	Interview and Observation	“. . . <i>ara gid sila na ya iban ya</i> poverty <i>ang iban gani ya</i> below poverty <i>gid</i> in terms of socio-economic status.”	
Classroom Management		Give students a collaborative learning process	Interview and Observation	“So from time to time <i>gina</i> group <i>ko sila</i> or <i>gina pares-pares</i> ”	
Student's Tactics	Learning	Peer tutoring	Interview and Observation	“So <i>makita mo man kis-a nga ga</i> peer tutoring <i>sila duwa sang</i> seatmate <i>niya</i> .”	
Instructional material needed in implementation of interdisciplinary contextualization		Activity book	Interview	“It must be associated with the pictures that are connected to the problems.”	

Table 2 shows the ratings of the activity book in general and in terms of physical aspects, objectives, learning activities, evaluation procedure, and integration of the interdisciplinary contextualization.

Table 2*Overall Acceptability Rating of the Interdisciplinary Contextualized Activity Book*

	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Description</i>
Overall Rating		0.23	3.44	<i>Highly Acceptable</i>
Physical Aspects	6	0.21	3.40	<i>Highly Acceptable</i>
Objectives	6	0.33	3.60	<i>Highly Acceptable</i>
Learning Activities	6	0.28	3.42	<i>Fairly Acceptable</i>
Evaluation Procedure	6	0.32	3.33	<i>Highly Acceptable</i>
Integration of Interdisciplinary Contextualization	6	0.33	3.45	<i>Highly Acceptable</i>

Note: Description is based on the following scale: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Acceptable), 1.76-3.25 (Fairly Acceptable), 1.00-1.75 (Unacceptable)

Table 3 summarizes the ratings obtained by the interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in statistics in physical aspects, pedagogical uses, evaluation procedure, relevance to the real-world context. The overall mean ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 0.39$).

Table 3*Overall Students' Satisfaction Rating of the Interdisciplinary Contextualized Activity Book*

	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Description</i>
Overall Rating		0.39	3.33	<i>Highly Satisfactory</i>
Physical Aspects	50	0.38	3.38	<i>Highly Satisfactory</i>
Pedagogical Uses	50	0.36	3.36	<i>Highly Satisfactory</i>
Evaluation Procedure	50	0.45	3.26	<i>Highly Satisfactory</i>
Relevance to the Real-World Context	50	0.46	3.31	<i>Highly Satisfactory</i>

Note: Description is based on the following scale: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Satisfactory), 1.76-3.25 (Fairly Satisfactory), 1.00-1.75 (Unsatisfactory)

DISCUSSION

After analyzing the data gathered from the interviews and observations, the researcher came into a conclusion to worked on a homework type of activity book that more on pictures wherein connected to the activity and with step-by-step process so that the students could answer on their own. This serves as remedy for the untackled topics for the fourth quarter.

The overall mean ($M = 4.69$, $SD = 0.22$) shows that the interdisciplinary contextualized activity book was “highly acceptable.” This means that the interdisciplinary contextualized activity book has highly met the experts’ expectations.

The overall mean ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 0.39$) means that the interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in selected topics in statistics was “highly satisfactory.” It means that the interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in selected topics in Statistics had highly met the students’ expectations.

With this, even the developed activity book is homework type and the topics involved have not yet been discussed but then the students were able to answer the activities because of the presence of different disciplines and the involvement of authenticity which they are experiencing.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Activity book is certainly one of the means and highly needed in implementing interdisciplinary contextualized mathematics 7.
The interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in statistics consists of the basic features such as objectives, summary of the important terms and concepts in the lesson, learning activities and iconnect.
2. The interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in statistics was acceptable in terms of physical aspects, objectives, learning activities, evaluation procedure, and integration of interdisciplinary contextualization as reflected in the evaluation by the experts.
3. The interdisciplinary contextualized activity book in statistics addressed the need of the students to have activities that aid to cope with the last topics of the school year which is about statistics that cannot be covered anymore due to insufficient time. Moreover, the students were satisfied in terms of physical aspects, pedagogical uses, evaluation procedure, and relevance to the real-world context.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. The LRMDs may consider interdisciplinary contextualized resource materials such as activity book.
2. IMCS may promote interdisciplinary contextualization to researches not only in the field of Mathematics but also to other subject areas.
3. School heads, policy-makers and curriculum designers may consider looking into the development of an integrated curriculum or integrated lessons.
4. The teachers, most especially the Mathematics teachers because most of the students found this subject difficult, may include other disciplines and real life contexts based on students' experiences in teaching.
5. To the students, especially those who are constructivist type, may be given an opportunity to learn and appreciate mathematical concepts through such material.
6. A research to compare the effectiveness of interdisciplinary contextualization not only in mathematics but also to the other subject area may be undertaken. A research study that may also use and improve the research instruments, especially the experts' evaluation form and students' satisfaction survey form, and test its reliability on a larger number of samples. Other researchers are encouraged to conduct similar investigations or even enhance this study not only in mathematics but also in other disciplines in which the experts will observe the actual implementation of the activity book.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A letter and consent form for the participants were provided. The consent form contains the assurance of their rights that will not be violated and will take their identity privately. Also, they were informed that their participation in this study was voluntary and will not cause them any harm. The results were used solely for research purposes only, ensuring integrity and ethical conduct throughout the study.

Acknowledgements

The researcher would like to extend her heartfelt gratitude for her success, this research study will be impossible without the following people who have to be mentioned: The researcher's dream to pursue her Master's degree became possible with the great help of Department of Science and Technology (DOST) led by Sec. Fortunato dela Peña and the DOST-Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI) headed by Dr. Josette T. Biyo through the National Consortium in Graduate Science and Mathematics Education (NCGSME) scholarship program; Dr. Rosemarie G. Felimon, her thesis adviser; panel members; instrument validators; principals of the two schools where the research conducted; evaluators; and participants.

To her mother, Mrs. Eva L. Elen, for her never-ending support and unceasing love. Mr. Eduardo A. Elen, her late father, who died during the making of this research study, her greatest inspiration and strength in pursuing this degree. Above all, the Almighty God for giving the strength, courage, and confidence required for the completion of this research study. Praise all the honor and glory to God Almighty!

REFERENCES

- Adebule, S. O. & Ayoola, O. O. (2015). Impact of instructional materials on students' academic performance in mathematics in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Pearl Research Journals*. 2 (1), 1-4. Retrieved from: <http://pearlresearchjournals.org/journals/rjesr/index.html>
- Adipo, A. J. (2015). *Mathematics in public primary schools in Siaya county, Kenya* (Published Masteral Thesis). University of Nairobi, Kenya.
- Akande, O.M. (1985). *Hints on teaching practice and general principles of education*. Lagos, OSKO Associates.
- Barrido, M. P. (2015). *Interactive notebook, students' study habits, and mathematics achievement*. (Unpublished Graduate Thesis). West Visayas State University, Iloilo, City.
- Curry, K., Jr., Wilson, E., Flowers, J., & Farin, C. (2012). Scientific basis vs. contextualized teaching and learning: The effect on the achievement of postsecondary students, *Journal of Agricultural Education*. 3 (1), 57–66. DOI: 10.5032/jae.2012.01057
- DOST-SEI & MATHTED. (2011a). Mathematics framework for Philippine basic education. *DOST-SEI & MATHTED*: Author.
- Heckman, P. & Weissglass, J. (1994). *Contextualized mathematics instruction: Moving beyond recent proposals*. Vancouver, British Columbia Canada: FL M Publishing Association.
- Nikitina, S. (2002). *Three strategies for interdisciplinary teaching: Contextualizing, conceptualizing, and problem-solving*. Interdisciplinary Studies Project. Retrieved from http://www.interdisciplinarystudiespz.org/pdf/Nikitina_Strategies_2002.pdf
- Nikitina, S. & Mansilla, V. B. (2003). *Three strategies for interdisciplinary math and science teaching: a case of the Illinois mathematics and science academy*. Project Zero, Harvard Graduate School of Education.
- Richey, R., Klein, J., & Nelson, W. (2015). *Developmental research: studies of instructional design and development*. Research Gate.
- Thompson, P. (1994). Concrete materials and teaching for mathematical understanding. *Arithmetic Teacher*, 41 (9), 556-558.